

AN INVENTORY MODEL FOR NON- INSTANTANEOUS DETERIORATING ITEMS UNDER WEIBULL DISTRIBUTION AND QUADRATIC DEMAND WITH TRADE CREDIT POLICY

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Abstract

This paper deals with the non-instantaneous deteriorating items following two parameter Weibull distribution rate and trade credit policy. The demand is considered as quadratic function of time. Shortages are allowed and partially backlogged. Sometimes demand spikes right after a product is introduced to the market. However, once an alternative is available on the market, demand begins to drop gradually. This form of demand is commonly referred to as quadratic demand. To increase profits, the supplier allows a reasonable delay in payment to the retailer. The trade credit policy refers to the allowable delay in payment. The mathematical model is divided into three categories. Case-I, $0 \leq M \leq t_0$, Case-II- $t_0 \leq M \leq t_k$ and Case-III, $t_k \leq M \leq L$. The model is demonstrated by numerical experiments, sensitivity analysis, and a graphical depiction.

Keywords: Inventory, Quadratic Demand, Weibull Distribution, Deterioration, Trade Credit.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study given in the article offers an inventory model for non-instantaneously decaying things under a specific set of parameters. The model is built around the Weibull distribution and quadratic demand, and it includes a trade credit policy, making it extremely relevant for current supply chain and inventory management. The present corporate climate, which is marked by fast shifts in customer demand and product lifecycles, necessitates sophisticated inventory management techniques. This work solves this need by developing an inventory model that takes into account non-instantaneous deterioration of goods. The model is unique in that it employs the Weibull distribution to estimate the rate of deterioration and a quadratic function to describe demand fluctuations over time. Inventory deterioration has a significant impact on product shelf life and usability. In many circumstances, such as pharmaceuticals, perishable foods, and even some technology things, deterioration occurs gradually rather than suddenly. This steady deterioration is well modelled by the two-parameter Weibull distribution, which is notable for its ability to reflect a wide range of failure rates. Furthermore, the quadratic demand function used in this model depicts a genuine scenario in which demand initially soars but then declines, frequently due to the appearance of replacements in the market. This tendency is especially pertinent in highly

competitive marketplaces or where technical developments make existing products less desirable.

The model's adoption of a trade credit policy reflects its real commercial ramifications. Trade credit, the practice of offering buyers deferred payment options, is a typical approach employed by suppliers to increase sales. It encourages shops to stock up on goods, knowing they have a limited time to sell the products before payment is due. This feature of the model is consistent with the strategic financial considerations that organisations must make regarding inventory management. The major goal is to create a mathematical model that will help businesses make intelligent inventory decisions while taking into account the intricate interplay of product deterioration, demand volatility, and finance methods such as trade credit. To demonstrate the model's efficacy, the methodology comprises numerical trials, sensitivity analysis, and graphical representations. This study has the potential to make a significant contribution to the field of inventory management by giving a sophisticated and practical strategy to dealing with non-instantaneous degrading commodities under varied demand conditions and financing techniques. It is especially relevant in today's dynamic market environment, when understanding and anticipating product life cycles and consumer demand patterns are critical to business success.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many inventory systems highly depend on deterioration. Generally, deterioration is defined as the loss of utility or marginal value of a good, which reduces its usefulness, as well as decay, damage, spoiling, evaporation, obsolescence, pilferage, and obsolescence. The majority of physical things deteriorate or decay with time; examples include pharmaceuticals, flammable liquids, blood banks, and so forth. Therefore, it is crucial to take into account the decay or deterioration of actual commodities in stock while modelling inventory since it is a very realistic factor. The important questions in inventory management to address the economic problem are when and how much to order. In order to do this, many criteria are used to build economic order quantity (EOQ) models. So first of all, the traditional EOQ model was created by (Ghare, 1963) under the presumptions of constant demand and constant deterioration rate. Numerous academics have expanded on their model with various conditions where the objective function is the profit function or cost function. Many studies believe that inventory products begin to degrade as soon as they are received into stock. (Çalışkan, 2021) created precise total cost functions for both the basic and backordering versions of the deteriorating items EOQ problem with compound interest. In fact, most products (including vegetables, fruit, seafood, and meat) would have a period during which their quality or original condition would be maintained, meaning that there is no deterioration would take place. A decaying inventory model with stock dependent demand has been constructed by (Kumar Bansal et al., 2018) as an EOQ inventory model. The cost of holding follows the learning curve. Shortages are permitted and are partially backlogged. The backlog rate is assumed to be an exponential function of time.

(Patriarca et al., 2020) provided an inventory control model for perishable commodities with a variable demand rate that, depending on the inventory rate, takes into account the possibility of backlogging and lost sales. Product quality is imperfect, and deterioration is described as a time-dependent variable. Many studies have been conducted using non-instantaneous deterioration rates with various types of limitations. To maximize overall profit per unit time, discover the optimal selling price, the length of time without an inventory shortfall, and the replenishment cycle duration all at the same time. A system of inventory for non-instantaneous degrading items with price-dependent demand is devised by (C. Te Yang et al., 2009), where shortages are allowed while partially backlogged, with the backlogging rate being variable and dependant on the waiting time for the next replacement. The mathematical modelling of deteriorating objects allows managers to analyze their inventory management systems in order to discover areas for improvement and quantify the possible benefits. (Pérez et al., 2019) created a deteriorating inventory model for optimizing the inventory control strategy of companies operating in sectors with deteriorating products, as well as for the overall financial impact of a company's policies on product price discounting and inventory shortages while taking the time value of money into account. Demand parameter plays a vital role in inventory management system. Inventory is directly depending upon the demand of the products. In past many inventory models are developed for the different types of demand. (Konstantaras & Skouri, 2009) developed an inventory model for deteriorating items that follows two parameter Weibull distribution and ramp type demand where shortages are allowed. (Pando et al., 2021) developed an inventory model with Stock-Dependent Demand Rate and Maximization of the Return on Investment. (Li et al., 2018) have been developed inventory model for the constant demand rate. (H. L. Yang, 2012) created a partial-backlog inventory lot-size model for degrading items with time-dependent demand, variable selling price, and purchase cost. (Naserabadi et al., 2014) created an inventory model for items with an unpredictable deterioration rate, a time-dependent demand rate with a nonincreasing function, and a permitted shortage in an inflationary environment. They assume that the consequent effect of inflation and time value of money is fuzzy in nature, and they also treat lead time as a fuzzy function of order quantity. The first is a fuzzy deterioration rate, and the second assumes that the deterioration rate is time dependent and follows the Weibull distribution with three known parameters. Sometimes, when a product launches in the market, the demand of that product increased linearly for some time. But when there is any substitute of the product available in the market, the demand of the product decreases exponentially. This type of demand is generally known as quadratic demand. We will consider the situation of the quadratic type demand in our research.

For many businesses, trade credit is a crucial resource for financing expansion. The company granting the credit specifies the number of days for which it is granted, and both the company granting the credit and the firm receiving it agree on this number. By the payment extension date, the business that received the credit could effectively sell the products and utilize the money received as credit to settle the obligation. Such a credit is offered to promote sales. The retailer can accumulate and earn interest on the encouraged sales income during this credit period. The supplier charges interest on the

outstanding balance in the event of a period of extension. As a result, the allowable delayed period indirectly lowers the holding cost. Additionally, the supplier's trade credit system pushes the store to purchase more merchandise. Trade credit is crucial to inventory management for both suppliers and retailers. Many researchers have developed the inventory model with the assumptions of trade credit policy or permissible delay in payment. (Udayakumar & Geetha, 2018) has presented an inventory model for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with trade credit policy where demand is known and constant. (Wu & Zhao, 2015) created an Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) model for deteriorating items with a current inventory-dependent and linearly growing time-varying demand under trade credit. (Annadurai, 2013) investigated an integrated inventory model under trade credit where the deterioration rate follows an exponential distribution. The demand rate is supposed to be a function of the selling price, and the allowable payment delay is determined by the order quantity. Model shortages are entirely backlogged. (Mahapatra et al., 2019) developed an economic order quantity model of decaying items, where demand is fuzzy and depends on promotional activity with full backorder for a specified time horizon. This model incorporates the learning effect in a fuzzy environment. A constant rate of deterioration is assumed. (Sundara Rajan & Uthayakumar, 2017) created an economic order quantity model to study the best replenishment methods for degrading items under inflation and trade credit. Over a finite planning horizon, demand rate is a linear function of selling price and falls negative exponentially with time. Shortages are permitted and are partially backlogged. (Jyoti Mohanty et al., 2046) created a stochastic deteriorating item inventory model by combining the concepts of preservation technology, time-varying ramp-type demand, and trade-credit finance in the form of allowed payment delay.

Item shortage is permitted and is a combination of partial backlog and missed sales. (Chang et al., 2016) developed an inventory model with trade credit policy, where demand is constant and shortages are not allowed. (Esmaili & Nasrabadi, 2021) provide an inventory model with inflation for a single-vendor multi-retailer supply chain in which both raw materials and final products deteriorate at separate and deterministic rates. The price has a downward sloping effect on completed product demand. The seller offers the retailers a payment delay. They look at two scenarios: (i) changes in the inflation rate as a Discrete-Time Markov Chain, and (ii) changes in the inflation rate without taking Markovian conditions into account. The vendor-retailer connection is represented by the Stackelberg game. For fixed lifespan products, (Sarkar et al., 2015) established the degradation function as a time dependent function. They took into account the retailer's partial trade-credit programme for customers. The supplier, on the other hand, provides the merchant with a complete trade credit period. The retailer provides a half trade-credit period to their consumers. Customers must pay for their purchases as soon as they receive them from the store. As a result, merchants can postpone payment until the end of the trade-credit period that they get from the supplier.

In this paper we have extended (Vandana & Sharma, 2016) by using Weibull distribution with non-instantaneous deterioration. An inventory model for deteriorating items with a trade credit policy using the Weibull distribution to model the rate of deterioration for the

items in the inventory. The trade credit policy would likely involve offering customers the option to purchase the items on credit, with the terms of the credit being based on the predicted remaining useful life of the item as determined by the Weibull distribution. The model would need to take into account the cost of the items, the cost of financing the credit, and the expected revenue from sales on credit in order to determine the optimal inventory levels and credit terms to offer.

Table 1: Key findings of the existing literature

Study/ Model	Key Features	Deterioration Rate	Demand Type	Trade Credit Policy	Gap/Unique Aspect
Ghare (1963)	Traditional EOQ Model	Constant	Constant	Not Considered	Lacked flexibility for varying demand and deterioration rates.
Çalışkan (2021)	EOQ with Compound Interest	Begins immediately	Not Specified	Not Considered	Focused on cost functions, didn't address varying demand scenarios.
Kumar Bansal et al. (2018)	EOQ with Stock Dependent Demand	After a certain period	Stock Dependent	Not Considered	Included learning curve in holding cost but didn't consider trade credit.
Patriarca et al. (2020)	Perishable Commodities Control	Time-Dependent	Variable	Not Considered	Addressed backlogging and lost sales, missed trade credit aspect.
C. Te Yang et al. (2009)	Price-Dependent Demand	Non-Instantaneous	Price-Dependent	Not Considered	Considered variable backlogging, lacked trade credit analysis.
Pérez et al. (2019)	Deteriorating Items Optimization	Not Specific	Not Specific	Not Considered	Focused on financial impact, didn't integrate trade credit or specific demand types.
Konstantaras & Skouri (2009)	Weibull Distribution with Ramp Demand	Weibull Distribution	Ramp Type	Not Considered	Introduced Weibull distribution, didn't explore trade credit.
Pando et al. (2021)	ROI Maximization	Not Specific	Stock-Dependent	Not Considered	Focused on ROI, didn't address trade credit or specific deterioration types.
Li et al. (2018)	Constant Demand Rate	Not Specific	Constant	Not Considered	Addressed constant demand, missed varying deterioration and trade credit.
H. L. Yang (2012)	Time-Dependent Demand	Time-Dependent	Time-Dependent	Not Considered	Integrated variable selling price, didn't consider trade credit.
Naserabadi et al. (2014)	Fuzzy Deterioration Rate	Fuzzy/Time-Dependent	Time-Dependent	Not Considered	Focused on inflation impact, didn't explore trade credit policy.

Udayakumar & Geetha (2018)	Non-Instantaneous Deterioration	Non-Instantaneous	Known and Constant	Considered	Integrated trade credit, didn't address varying or uncertain demand.
Vandana & Sharma B (2016)	Quadratic Demand	Non-Instantaneous	Quadratic	Considered	Weibull distribution in deterioration, Finite replenishment cycle.
Wu & Zhao (2015)	EOQ for Deteriorating Items	Not Specific	Inventory-Dependent & Time-Varying	Considered	Combined trade credit with time-varying demand, didn't specify deterioration type.
Annadurai (2013)	Integrated Model under Trade Credit	Exponential	Selling Price Function	Considered	Explored trade credit with exponential deterioration, didn't address non-linear demand types.
Mahapatra et al. (2019)	Fuzzy Demand with Promotional Activity	Constant	Fuzzy and Promotional Activity Dependent	Considered	Focused on promotional activity impact, lacked specific deterioration modeling.
Sundara Rajan & Uthayakumar (2017)	Degrading Items under Inflation	Not Specific	Linear Function of Selling Price	Considered	Addressed inflation and trade credit, didn't focus on deterioration specifics.
Jyoti Mohanty et al. (2046)	Stochastic Model with Preservation Technology	Not Specific	Ramp-Type	Considered	Combined preservation technology and trade-credit, lacked specific deterioration rate analysis.
Chang et al. (2016)	Constant Demand Model	Not Specific	Constant	Considered	Focused on constant demand and trade credit, missed varying deterioration rates.
Esmaili & Nasrabadi (2021)	Single-Vendor Multi-Retailer Model	Separate for Raw Materials and Final Products	Downward Sloping	Considered	Integrated inflation and trade credit, didn't focus on non-linear demand types.
Sarkar et al. (2015)	Fixed Lifespan Products	Time-Dependent	Not Specified	Considered	Targeted fixed lifespan products, lacked comprehensive demand modeling.

3. NOTATIONS AND ASSUMPTION

Below are the suggested inventory model's notations and assumptions:

3.1 Assumptions:

- Demand rate is quadratic function of time.
- A single warehouse and a single item are considered.

- Shortages are not permitted.
- Lead time is assumed to be zero.
- The deterioration rate follows the two parameter Weibull distribution.
- There is no repair or replenishment of the deteriorated items during the inventory cycle.
- The inventory is replenished only one in each cycle.
- The retailer can increase returns and produce interest, which will be followed by customer payments in purchasing costs from the retailer in anticipation of the dealer's permissible payment time being completed.

3.2 Notations:

- $D(t) = a + bt + ct^2$: Quadratic demand rate where, $a > b$ and $a > c$.
- $\theta(t) = \alpha\beta t^{\beta-1}$: The Weibull distribution deterioration rate where $0 < \alpha < 1$ the scale parameter and $\beta > 0$ is the shape parameter.
- M =Trade credit offered by supplier in months.
- I_p = Interest charges per \$ per month.
- I_e =Interest earned per \$ in stocks per month.
- $I_1(t)$ = The non-decaying inventory level in duration $[0, t_0]$.
- $I_2(t)$ = The inventory level in which demand and deterioration level goes to '0' in duration $[t_0, L]$. $[L = t_0 + t_k]$
- t_0 = Time period in which product maintain their freshness.
- t_k = The time period in which the deterioration in the product takes place.
- L = Cycle Length.
- Q_k = Ordered Quantity per Cycle.
- O_c = Ordering Cost per order.
- θ_c = Deterioration Cost per unit per unit time.
- H_c = Holding Cost per unit per unit time.
- P_c = Cost of purchasing per item
- R_c =Cost of sales revenue per item
- $Ct(t, L)$ = Total Cost.

4. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION OF MODEL

Let Q_k be the inventory level at time t . The inventory level is assumed to be affected by demand only and there is no deterioration within the period $(0, t_0)$. After some time, the deterioration starts during the interval (t_0, t_k) . At t_k , the inventory level drops to zero, and in the period (t_k, L) there is a shortage. The model can be further developed by including additional assumptions and notation, such as the rate of deterioration, the cost of acquiring additional inventory, and the cost of lost sales due to the shortages. These additional factors can be used to optimize the inventory management strategy and minimize the overall cost of the system. The inventory levels of the model are governed by the following differential equations:

$$\frac{dI_1(t)}{dt} = -D(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dI_2(t)}{dt} + \theta(t)I_2(t) = -D(t), \quad t_0 \leq t \leq t_k \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dI_3(t)}{dt} = -e^{-\mu(L-t)}D(t), \quad t_k \leq t \leq L \quad (3)$$

Where $D(t)$ is quadratic demand rate.

$$D(t) = a + bt + ct^2$$

From equation (1), we get;

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dI_1(t)}{dt} &= -(a + bt + ct^2) \\ I_1(t) &= -\left(at + \frac{bt^2}{2} + \frac{ct^3}{3}\right) + c_1 \end{aligned}$$

With Boundary conditions, $I_1(t) = Q_k$ at $t = 0$

Then,

$$Q_k = c_1$$

$$I_1(t) = Q_k - \left(at + \frac{bt^2}{2} + \frac{ct^3}{3}\right) \quad (4)$$

On solving equation (2), we have;

$$\frac{dI_2(t)}{dt} + \alpha\beta t^{\beta-1}I_2(t) = -(a + bt + ct^2)$$

$$I_2(t) = -e^{-\alpha t^\beta} \left[at + \frac{bt^2}{2} + \frac{ct^3}{3} + \alpha \left(\frac{t^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) \right] + c_2 e^{-\alpha t^\beta} \quad (5)$$

If $I_2(t) = 0$ at $t = t_k$ then

$$0 = -e^{-\alpha t_k^\beta} \left[at_k + \frac{bt_k^2}{2} + \frac{bt_k^3}{3} + \alpha \left(\frac{t_k^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) \right] + c_2 e^{-\alpha t_k^\beta}$$

$$c_2 = \left[at_k + \frac{bt_k^2}{2} + \frac{bt_k^3}{3} + \alpha \left(\frac{t_k^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) \right]$$

Putting the value of c_2 in equation (5)

$$I_2(t) = -e^{-\alpha t^\beta} \left[at + \frac{bt^2}{2} + \frac{ct^3}{3} + \alpha \left(\frac{t^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) \right]$$

$$+ \left[at_k + \frac{bt_k^2}{2} + \frac{bt_k^3}{3} + \alpha \left(\frac{t_k^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) \right] e^{-\alpha t^\beta}$$

$$I_2(t) = e^{-\alpha t^\beta} \left[a(t_k - t) + \frac{b(t_k^2 - t^2)}{2} + \frac{c(t_k^3 - t^3)}{3} + \alpha \left(\frac{t_k^{\beta+1} - t^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+2} - t^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+3} - t^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) \right]$$

(6)

Now, considering continuity of $I(t)$ at $t = t_0$ it follows from the equation (4) and (6)

$$I_1(t_0) = I_2(t_0)$$

We get,

$$Q_k - \left(at_0 + \frac{bt_0^2}{2} + \frac{ct_0^3}{3} \right)$$

$$= e^{-\alpha t_0^\beta} \left[a(t_k - t_0) + \frac{b(t_k^2 - t_0^2)}{2} + \frac{c(t_k^3 - t_0^3)}{3} \right.$$

$$\left. + \alpha \left(\frac{t_k^{\beta+1} - t_0^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+2} - t_0^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+3} - t_0^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) \right]$$

$$Q_k = e^{-\alpha t_0^\beta} \left[a(t_k - t_0) + \frac{b(t_k^2 - t_0^2)}{2} + \frac{c(t_k^3 - t_0^3)}{3} + \alpha \left\{ \frac{t_k^{\beta+1} - t_0^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+2} - t_0^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+3} - t_0^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right\} \right] + at_0 + \frac{bt_0^2}{2} + \frac{ct_0^3}{3}$$

(7)

Using equation (7) in equation (4)

$$I_1(t) = e^{-\alpha t^\beta} \left[a(t_k - t_0) + \frac{b(t_k^2 - t_0^2)}{2} + \frac{c(t_k^3 - t_0^3)}{3} + \alpha \left\{ \frac{t_k^{\beta+1} - t_0^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+2} - t_0^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+3} - t_0^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right\} \right]$$

$$+ a(t_0 - t) + \frac{b(t_0^2 - t^2)}{2} + \frac{c(t_0^3 - t^3)}{3}$$

(8)

From equation (3), we get

$$I_3(t) = - \left[(1 - \mu L) \left(at + \frac{bt^2}{2} + \frac{ct^2}{3} \right) + \mu \left(\frac{at^2}{2} + \frac{bt^3}{3} + \frac{ct^4}{4} \right) \right]$$

(9)

4.1 The ordering cost per cycle is

$$OC = O_c \quad (10)$$

4.2 The deterioration cost per cycle is:

$$DC = D_c \int_{t_0}^{t_{k1}} I_2(t) dt$$

$$DC = D_c \left[\frac{at_k^2}{2} + \frac{bt_k^3}{3} + \frac{ct_k^4}{4} - a \left(t_k t_0 - \frac{t_0^2}{2} \right) - \frac{b}{2} \left(t_k^2 t_0 - \frac{t_0^3}{3} \right) - \frac{c}{3} \left(t_k^3 t_0 - \frac{t_0^4}{4} \right) + \alpha \left\{ \left(\frac{t_k^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} + \frac{t_k^{\beta+4}}{\beta+4} \right) - \frac{1}{\beta+1} \left(\frac{at_k^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{bt_k^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} + \frac{ct_k^{\beta+4}}{\beta+4} \right) - t_0 \left\{ \frac{1}{\beta+1} \left(t_k^{\beta+1} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+1}}{\beta+2} \right) + \frac{1}{\beta+2} \left(t_k^{\beta+2} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+2}}{\beta+3} \right) + \frac{1}{\beta+3} \left(t_k^{\beta+3} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+3}}{\beta+4} \right) \right\} + a \left(\frac{t_0^{\beta+1} t_k}{\beta+1} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} \right) + \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{t_0^{\beta+1} t_k^2}{\beta+1} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) + \frac{c}{3} \left(\frac{t_0^{\beta+1} t_k^3}{\beta+1} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+4}}{\beta+4} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (11)$$

4.3 The inventory holding cost per cycle is:

$$HC = H_c \left[\int_0^{t_0} I_1(t) dt + \int_{t_0}^{t_{k1}} I_2(t) dt \right]$$

$$HC = H_c \left[a \left(t_{k1} t_0 - t_0^2 \right) + \frac{b}{2} \left(t_{k1}^2 t_0 - t_0^3 \right) + \frac{c}{3} \left(t_{k1}^3 t_0 - t_0^4 \right) + \alpha \left(\frac{t_{k1}^{\beta+1} t_0 - t_0^{\beta+2}}{\beta+1} + \frac{t_{k1}^{\beta+2} t_0 - t_0^{\beta+3}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_{k1}^{\beta+3} t_0 - t_0^{\beta+4}}{\beta+3} \right) - \alpha \left\{ a \left(t_{k1} t_0^{\beta+1} - t_0^{\beta+2} \right) + \frac{b}{2} \left(t_{k1}^2 t_0^{\beta+1} - t_0^{\beta+3} \right) + \frac{c}{3} \left(t_{k1}^3 t_0^{\beta+1} - t_0^{\beta+4} \right) \right\} + \frac{at_{k1}^2}{2} + \frac{bt_{k1}^3}{3} + \frac{ct_{k1}^4}{4} - a \left(t_{k1} t_0 - \frac{t_0^2}{2} \right) - \frac{b}{2} \left(t_{k1}^2 t_0 - \frac{t_0^3}{3} \right) - \frac{c}{3} \left(t_{k1}^3 t_0 - \frac{t_0^4}{4} \right) + \alpha \left\{ \left(\frac{t_{k1}^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{t_{k1}^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} + \frac{t_{k1}^{\beta+4}}{\beta+4} \right) - \frac{1}{\beta+1} \left(\frac{at_{k1}^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} + \frac{bt_{k1}^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} + \frac{ct_{k1}^{\beta+4}}{\beta+4} \right) - t_0 \left\{ \frac{1}{\beta+1} \left(t_{k1}^{\beta+1} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+1}}{\beta+2} \right) + \frac{1}{\beta+2} \left(t_{k1}^{\beta+2} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+2}}{\beta+3} \right) + \frac{1}{\beta+3} \left(t_{k1}^{\beta+3} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+3}}{\beta+4} \right) \right\} + a \left(\frac{t_0^{\beta+1} t_{k1}}{\beta+1} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+2}}{\beta+2} \right) + \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{t_0^{\beta+1} t_{k1}^2}{\beta+1} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+3}}{\beta+3} \right) + \frac{c}{3} \left(\frac{t_0^{\beta+1} t_{k1}^3}{\beta+1} - \frac{t_0^{\beta+4}}{\beta+4} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (12)$$

4.4 Backorder cost per cycle is: $BC = B_c \int_{t_{k1}}^L -I_3(t) dt$

$$BC = B_c \left[(1 - \mu L) \left\{ \frac{a}{2} (L^2 - t_{k1}^2) + \frac{b}{6} (L^3 - t_{k1}^3) + \frac{c}{12} (L^4 - t_{k1}^4) \right\} + \mu \left\{ \frac{a}{6} (L^3 - t_{k1}^3) + \frac{b}{12} (L^4 - t_{k1}^4) + \frac{c}{20} (L^5 - t_{k1}^5) \right\} \right] \quad (13)$$

4.5 Interest payable

For each cycle, we need to consider the cases where the length of the credit period is longer or shorter than, the length of time in which the product exhibits no deterioration

(t_0) and the length of the period, with positive inventory of the item(t_{k1}). So, we have three cases

$$I_p = \begin{cases} I_{p1}, & 0 \leq M \leq t_0 \\ I_{p2}, & t_0 \leq M \leq t_{k1} \\ I_{p3}, & t_{k1} \leq M \leq L \end{cases}$$

Case-1: For $0 \leq M \leq t_0$. In this case, payment for items is settled and the retailer starts paying the capital opportunity cost for the items

$$I_{p1} = p_1 I_p \left(\int_0^M I_1(t) dt + \int_M^{t_0} I_2(t) dt \right)$$

Case-2: For $t_0 \leq M \leq t_{k1}$. In this case the interest payable is

$$I_{p2} = p_2 I_p \left(\int_M^{t_{k1}} I_2(t) dt \right)$$

Case-3: For $t_{k1} \leq M \leq L$ In this case, there is no interest payable charged, i.e.

$$I_{p3} = 0$$

4.6 Interest earned (I_E) - During the time, when the account is not settled, the retailer sells the goods and continues to accumulate sales revenue and earns the interest with rate i . Therefore, the interest earned per year is

$$I_E = \begin{cases} I_{E1}, & 0 \leq M \leq t_0 \\ I_{E2}, & t_0 \leq M \leq t_k \\ I_{E3}, & t_{k1} \leq M \leq L \end{cases}$$

Case-1: For $0 \leq M \leq t_0$. In this case, the interest earned is

$$I_{E1} = p I_e \left(\int_0^M D(t) t dt \right)$$

Case-2: For $t_0 \leq M \leq t_{k1}$. In this case the interest earned is

$$I_{E2} = p I_e \left(\int_{t_0}^M D(t) t dt \right)$$

Case-3: For $t_{k1} \leq M \leq L$ In this case, there is no interest earned is

$$I_{E3} = p I_e \int_0^{t_0} D(t) t dt + (M - t_{k1}) \int_0^{t_0} D(t) t dt$$

Therefore, the total minimum relevant cost per unit time is denoted by TC is given by

$$TC(t_k) = \begin{cases} TC_1(t_k) = \frac{OC + DC + HC + BC + I_{p1} - I_{E1}}{L} & 0 \leq M \leq t_0 \\ TC_2(t_k) = \frac{OC + DC + HC + BC + I_{p2} - I_{E2}}{L} & t_0 \leq M \leq t_k \\ TC_3(t_k) = \frac{OC + DC + HC + BC + I_{p3} - I_{E3}}{L} & t_k \leq M \leq L \end{cases}$$

5. SOLUTION PROCEDURE

Since TC_1 , TC_2 and TC_3 are continuous and well defined. Now we have to check the optimality for each case.

Case-1: For $0 \leq M \leq t_0$ To obtain the first order necessary condition for TC_1 to be minimum, we differentiate TC_1 with respect to t_{k1} and take the result equal to zero, i.e.

$$\frac{\partial TC_1(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0 \quad (4.1)$$

Therefore we find the value of t_{k1}^* from (4.1) and differentiate (4.1) again with respect to t_k i.e. $\frac{\partial^2 TC_1(t_k)}{\partial t_k^2} = \omega_1$. Since the two derivative expression is highly non-linear.

Thus, we are not writing the whole expression of ω_1 . Therefore, we have the following lemma:

Lemma- 4.1. 1. When $\frac{\partial TC_1(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0$ at $t_{k1} = t_{k1}^* \in [M, L)$, then $TC_1(t_k)$ not only exists but unique and minimum if $\omega_1 > 0$.

Proof: It is obvious from (4.1), if we put $\frac{\partial TC_1(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0$ and find an optimum value of t_k i.e. $t_{k1}^* \in [M, L)$, then $TC_1(t_k)$ exists and having the unique value. And if $\frac{\partial^2 TC_1(t_k)}{\partial t_k^2} = \omega_1 > 0$, then $TC_1(t_k)$ has its minimum value.

2. If $\omega_1 > 0$, then the $TC_1(t_k)$ has its minimum at point $t_{k1} = t_{k1}^* = M$

Proof: Here ω_1 is differentiable and if $\omega_1 > 0$ then ω_1 is monotonically increasing function. Hence it can have at most one zero and i.e., $\lim_{t_k \rightarrow \infty} \omega_1 = \infty$. Thus, the value of $TC_1(t_k)$ is monotonically increasing function of t_k , if $TC_1(t_k)$ will not have any stationary point in $[M, \infty)$ i.e., $t_k < M$. Thus, the value of t_{k1}^* is unique.

Case-2: For $t_0 \leq M \leq t_k$ To obtain the first order necessary condition for TC_2 to be minimum, we differentiate TC_2 with respect to t_{k2} and take the result equal to zero, i.e.

$$\frac{\partial TC_2(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0 \quad (4.2)$$

Therefore we find the value of t_{k2}^* from (4.2) and differentiate (4.2) again with respect to t_k i.e. $\frac{\partial^2 TC_2(t_k)}{\partial t_k^2} = \omega_2$. Since the two derivative expression is highly non-linear.

Thus, we are not writing the whole expression of ω_2 .

Therefore, we have the following lemma:

Lemma- 4.2. 1. When $\frac{\partial TC_2(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0$ at $t_{k2} = t_{k2}^* \in [M, L)$, then $TC_2(t_k)$ not only exists but unique and minimum if $\omega_2 > 0$.

Proof: It is obvious from (4.2), if we put $\frac{\partial TC_2(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0$ and find an optimum value of t_k i.e. $t_{k2}^* \in [M, L)$, then $TC_2(t_k)$ exists and having the unique value. And if $\frac{\partial^2 TC_2(t_k)}{\partial t_k^2} = \omega_2 > 0$, then $TC_2(t_k)$ has its minimum value.

2. If $\omega_2 > 0$, then the $TC_2(t_k)$ has its minimum at point $t_{k2} = t_{k2}^* = M$

Proof: Here ω_1 is differentiable and if $\omega_2 > 0$ then ω_2 is monotonically increasing function. Hence it can have at most one zero and i.e., $\lim_{t_k \rightarrow \infty} \omega_2 = \infty$.

Thus, the value of $TC_2(t_k)$ is monotonically increasing function of t_k , if $TC_2(t_k)$ will not have any stationary point in $[M, \infty)$ i.e., $t_k < M$. Thus, the value of t_{k2}^* is unique.

Case-3: For $t_k \leq M \leq L$ - To obtain the first order necessary condition for TC_3 to be minimum, we differentiate TC_3 with respect to t_{k3} and take the result equal to zero, i.e.

$$\frac{\partial TC_3(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

Therefore we find the value of t_{k3}^* from (4.3) and differentiate (4.3) again with respect to t_k i.e. $\frac{\partial^2 TC_3(t_k)}{\partial t_k^2} = \omega_3$. Since the two derivative expression is highly non-linear.

Thus, we are not writing the whole expression of ω_3 . Therefore, we have the following lemma:

Lemma- 4.3. 1. When $\frac{\partial TC_3(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0$ at $t_{k3} = t_{k3}^* \in [0, M)$, then $TC_3(t_k)$ not only exists but unique and minimum if $\omega_3 > 0$.

Proof: It is obvious from (4.3), if we put $\frac{\partial TC_3(t_k)}{\partial t_k} = 0$ and find an optimum value of t_k i.e. $t_{k3}^* \in [0, M)$, then $TC_3(t_k)$ exists and having the unique value. And if $\frac{\partial^2 TC_3(t_k)}{\partial t_k^2} = \omega_3 > 0$, then $TC_3(t_k)$ has its minimum value.

2. If $\omega_3 > 0$, then the $TC_3(t_k)$ has its minimum at point $t_{k3} = t_{k3}^* = M$

6. COMPUTATIONAL ALGORITHM

In this part, we discuss the procedure of finding the optimal solution of t_{k3}^* .

The procedure is as follows-

Step-1. To find the minimum of $TC_1(t_k)$ as:

- a. Find $\frac{\partial TC_1(t_k)}{\partial t_k}$ and equate it at 0, then find t_k .

b. Compute ω_1 . If $\omega_1 > 0$, then set $t_{k1} = t_{k1}^*$, otherwise move to next step.

c. Set $t_{k1} = t_{k1}^* = M$ and find the value of $TC_1(t_k)$.

Step-2. To find the minimum of $TC_2(t_k)$ as:

a. Find $\frac{\partial TC_2(t_k)}{\partial t_k}$ and equate it at 0, then find t_k .

b. Compute ω_2 . If $\omega_2 > 0$, then set $t_{k2} = t_{k2}^*$, otherwise move to next step.

c. Set $t_{k2} = t_{k2}^* = M$ and find the value of $TC_2(t_k)$.

Step-3. Find the minimum of $TC_3(t_k)$ as:

a. Find $\frac{\partial TC_3(t_k)}{\partial t_k}$ and equate it at 0, then find t_k .

b. Compute ω_1 . If $\omega_1 > 0$, then set $t_{k3} = t_{k3}^*$, otherwise move to next step.

c. Set $t_{k3} = t_{k3}^* = M$ and find the value of $TC_3(t_k)$.

Step-4. To find the minimum of $TC(t_k)$ we will find the minimum of $TC_1(t_k)$, $TC_2(t_k)$ and $TC_3(t_k)$ and then select the optimal value of $t_k = t_k^*$ accordingly.

Step-5. Find the total relevant cost.

7. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS:

We took a numerical example from (Vandana & Sharma, 2016) $a = 25$ per unit, $b = 15$ per unit, $c = 10$ per unit, consider $O_c = 250$ per unit per order, $H_c = 15$ per unit, $D_c = 0.4$ per unit, $B_c = 30$ per unit, $I_p = 1.2$, $I_e = 0.12$ per year, $p_1 = 80$ per year, $p = 85$ per unit, $L = 1$ Year, $\mu = 0.006$ $t_0 = 0.5$ per year, $\alpha = 0.01$, $\beta = 1$.

For Case-1: $M = 0.05$ month

When the value of M is set to 0.05 and the equation (4.1) is solved, a positive value ω_1 is obtained. This result suggests that the optimal solution for t_{k1} is not only feasible but also unique, and its value is determined to be $t_{k1} = t_{k1}^* = 0.386357$ per year. Furthermore, the total cost is calculated to be $TC_1 = 653.7981$ per year, and the total order quantity Q is determined to be $Q^* = 20.0215$ per unit.

Case-2: $M = 0.12$ month

When the value of M is set to 0.12 and the equation (4.2) is solved, a positive value ω_2 is obtained. It is concluded from this conclusion that the ideal solution for t_{k1} is $t_{k1} = t_{k2}^* = 0.451461$ per year, and it is both feasible and unique. In addition, the total order quantity Q is found to be $Q^* = 20.30614$ per unit, and the total cost is computed as $TC_2 = 583.7981$ per year.

Case-3: $M = 0.80$ month

A positive number ω_3 is found by solving equation (4.3) with the value of M set to 0.80. The value of the best solution for t_{k1} is found to be $t_{k1} = t_{k1}^* = 0.619143$ per year, which

indicates that it is both unique and feasible. Furthermore, the total cost is calculated to be $TC_3 = 471.8774$ per year, and the total order quantity Q is determined to be $Q^* = 22.03219$ per unit. Now we will find the total optimal cost from step (4).

Therefore total optimal cost $TC(t_k) = \min\{TC_1(t_k), TC_2(t_k), TC_3(t_k)\}$ i.e. $TC(t_k) = \min\{653.7981, 583.7981, 471.8774\}$ and choose the optimum replenishment cycle time as a result. We got the optimal time length $t_{k1} = t_{k3}^* = 0.619143$ per year.

Sensitivity analysis is performed by changing parameters -50%, -25%, 25% and 50%. Only one parameter is changed at once while other parameters remain unchanged. The result of sensitivity analysis is shown in Table-2, Table-3 and Table-4.

Table 2: Sensitivity analysis of objective function TC_1

Parameter	% Change in Parameter	Change in		Q_k
		t_k	TC_1	
a	-50	0.332414	649.6053	17.2230
	-25	0.212350	663.8781	28.3277
	25	0.113625	694.5143	42.3053
	50	0.094361	729.0702	59.2786
b	-50	0.312562	646.3908	19.3625
	-25	0.297841	661.1632	21.8164
	25	0.159952	673.2065	22.6114
	50	0.003651	682.3486	23.3641
c	-50	0.321546	647.8529	20.9544
	-25	0.316242	653.7064	21.3801
	25	0.303496	658.5373	21.6354
	50	0.290102	663.4536	21.9902
O_c	-50	0.305219	645.2120	21.3516
	-25	0.307642	669.5993	21.5846
	25	0.309845	681.9529	22.0542
	50	0.311358	695.1965	22.4284
H_c	-50	0.406255	662.7304	21.8895
	-25	0.400890	668.6022	22.4851
	25	0.395269	674.4315	22.9284
	50	0.390183	679.2535	23.2612
D_c	-50	0.415146	664.4081	23.6250
	-25	0.405503	665.8595	23.9023
	25	0.393769	666.4119	24.4627
	50	0.385087	666.8257	24.8963
B_c	-50	0.417562	663.8679	23.4531
	-25	0.459647	664.1244	23.1325
	25	0.504756	665.5871	23.0014
	50	0.560483	595.0887	22.9453
M	-50	0.391281	659.9552	21.3125
	-25	0.385677	653.7981	20.9845
	25	0.380365	657.9718	20.1254
	50	0.376253	652.7558	20.7522

Table 3: Sensitivity analysis of objective function TC_2

Parameter	% Change in Parameter	Change in		Q_k
		t_k	TC_2	
a	-50	0.429937	530.0075	15.9176
	-25	0.407490	561.6371	19.3277
	25	0.398625	586.3811	22.3053
	50	0.367629	620.2971	24.2786
b	-50	0.433411	569.2546	16.7952
	-25	0.403660	579.8461	17.8466
	25	0.370154	588.2942	19.9463
	50	0.333219	594.2556	21.7695
c	-50	0.415468	575.3255	19.8314
	-25	0.407641	579.7685	20.4690
	25	0.398485	583.9636	21.0015
	50	0.383341	586.4871	21.7655
O_c	-50	0.426201	583.3110	20.8101
	-25	0.428756	591.8321	21.3611
	25	0.430491	603.1551	21.8122
	50	0.432364	615.7710	22.0123
H_c	-50	0.435314	582.9100	21.7854
	-25	0.419693	588.5614	22.3142
	25	0.394771	594.2371	22.8124
	50	0.389014	599.3977	23.1120
D_c	-50	0.526237	582.3117	19.4312
	-25	0.516694	583.7625	19.8451
	25	0.494868	584.1110	20.3114
	50	0.486196	584.9236	20.7836
B_c	-50	0.402151	580.8679	19.0021
	-25	0.437440	582.1244	19.5114
	25	0.463200	585.5871	19.9325
	50	0.490114	589.0887	18.6691
M	-50	0.460120	587.9552	19.9510
	-25	0.453221	583.7981	19.3511
	25	0.448408	581.9718	18.9451
	50	0.435127	577.7558	18.3666

Table 4: Sensitivity analysis of objective function TC_3

Parameter	% Change in Parameter	Change in		Q_k
		t_k	TC_3	
a	-50	0.634321	380.3251	17.0745
	-25	0.490216	431.8479	33.3558
	25	0.311661	479.5114	54.7141
	50	0.104252	496.0074	65.3277
b	-50	0.648654	410.1204	20.9927
	-25	0.584248	451.7895	22.8136
	25	0.414502	486.0151	24.6948
	50	0.336201	510.0272	26.0097
c	-50	0.678410	466.0031	21.9901

	-25	0.651412	472.2410	22.2013
	25	0.624034	477.3267	22.5109
	50	0.590102	483.5001	22.7693
O_c	-50	0.673012	476.3214	20.9142
	-25	0.675348	480.9625	21.1023
	25	0.677491	489.7055	21.3514
	50	0.681786	497.8050	21.5973
H_c	-50	0.602347	461.3251	21.9152
	-25	0.575261	470.4590	22.3524
	25	0.553140	477.6817	22.8451
	50	0.513204	482.9101	23.0012
D_c	-50	0.652418	473.1001	23.3223
	-25	0.641542	473.5361	23.6158
	25	0.633417	473.9794	23.9847
	50	0.629307	474.2221	24.3401
B_c	-50	0.663754	479.0301	19.4361
	-25	0.690011	480.8914	19.5947
	25	0.724215	481.9471	19.1004
	50	0.740333	483.0033	18.7670
M	-50	0.653614	476.2814	24.3014
	-25	0.618770	471.8774	23.8941
	25	0.580061	465.8933	22.3673
	50	0.561117	460.4001	21.9871

Figure 1: Variation in TC1 with respect to different parameters $a, b, c, O_c, H_c, D_c, B_c, M$

Figure 2: Variation in TC2 with respect to different parameters $a, b, c, O_c, H_c, D_c, B_c, M$

Figure 3: Variation in TC3 with respect to different parameters $a, b, c, O_c, H_c, D_c, B_c, M$

Figure-1, Figure-2 and Figure-3 are showing the variation in total cost TC1, TC2 and TC3 respectively. As seen in above Figures, we can say that TC_1 do not impact much until the

parameters changes to 25% and deviation can only be seen after 25% change in parameters, where B_c and a mostly affects TC_1 . In case of TC_2 we observed that TC_2 is highly affected with a . As slight change in demand can result in rapid increase in total cost, similar case can be seen with other parameter on TC_2 except trade credit " M ". TC_2 is in negative correlation with Trade Credit " M ". Coming to TC_3 , almost all parameter remains unchanged, except " a " and " b ", if we decrease parameter a and b , TC_3 can be lowered.

Concluding from above Figures, we can say that, "Case-2 is much affected by the parameters". It is indicating that the scenario of $t_0 \leq M \leq t_{k1}$. In our investigation, the impact of parameter " a " exhibited more pronounced variations in TC_2 compared to TC_1 and TC_3 . The observed data underscores a distinctive sensitivity of TC_2 to changes in parameter a , suggesting its potential significance in influencing the system's dynamics and performance.

8. RESULTS

The observations of the inventory model are complex, as they dynamically react to a range of cost parameters:

- a) To begin with, alterations in demand parameters (a, b, c) have a direct impact on t_k , resulting in an expedited stock turnover. As a consequence, both the overall expenditure (TC) and the volume of merchandise (Q) managed increase. It is important to note that TC and Q are highly sensitive to changes in the demand parameter ' a '. This implies that the cost and volume of the inventory can be significantly affected by even little adjustments made to this parameter. Conversely, these metrics demonstrate a decreased susceptibility to fluctuations in the ' c ' parameter.
- b) Regarding the cost parameters, a rise in ordering cost (O_c) indicates that t_k is extending. This means that higher costs for placing orders lead to fewer but bigger orders, which raises the total cost and quantity. Parallel to this, a rise in holding cost (H_c) signifies higher costs related to inventory storage, which in turn prompts a decrease in t_k to offset these costs. This change results in more orders being placed, which drives up the price and quantity overall. Analogously, the degradation cost (D_c) shows a similar pattern of behavior: as this cost rises, t_k falls to offset the loss resulting from decaying products; hence, more frequent orders are required, driving up both the total cost and quantity.
- c) An increase in backorder cost (B_c), which represents a tactic to lower unmet customer expectations (backorders) by producing fewer, bigger orders, results in an extension of t_k . The total cost and quantity of items rise as a result of this adjustment. Finally, an extension of the trade credit term (M) gives merchants a longer time frame to pay for their purchases, which causes t_k to decrease. Retailers are able to maintain lower stock levels and improve their cash flow management because to this decrease in inventory cycle time, which affects both quantity and overall cost.

9. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Manage mentally, the findings derived from the inventory model are of considerable importance.

- a) A decrease in inventory cycle time L is necessary to match sales (Q) and calculate quantity and total cost (TC) in response to an increase in demand parameters, which signify a growth in market demand. This means that managers need to be extremely careful with the demand parameter 'a' because of its significant influence on the size of inventory and associated costs.
- b) Elevated ordering costs can cause inventory cycles to lengthen, which raises overall costs and forces managers to place larger orders. Strategic planning is required to maintain sufficient stock levels while balancing the increased expenses.
- c) Similarly, higher holding costs result in a greater need to pass over inventory quickly to avoid cost increases, which raises total costs and the frequency of orders. Managers should think about renegotiating terms with suppliers or looking at more efficient storage solutions in order to match their inventory strategy with the situation.
- d) An increase in the costs associated with deterioration suggests that perishable or biodegradable items need to be rotated more quickly, which would impact order frequency and total cost. In their efforts to minimize degrading losses, managers also need to take into account the higher costs that come with placing more orders. Increased backorder costs highlight how important it is to effectively manage customer demand. Managers may be forced to increase inventory levels in order to avoid missing sales, which may affect the total cost and volume of inventory.
- e) There is a strategic advantage to extending trade credit periods. It permits businesses to defer payments, which makes it easier to manage lower inventory levels and lower the total cost and quantity.

10. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have extended (Vandana & Sharma, 2016) by using Weibull distribution with non-instantaneous deterioration. An inventory model for deteriorating items with a trade credit policy using the Weibull distribution to model the rate of deterioration for the items in the inventory. This concept stands out because it includes a credit programme for commercial transactions. It considers the postponed payment arrangements that are common in today's business transactions between distributors and retailers. This approach is particularly relevant since it tackles the fact that retailers could not get payment for their orders right away, which affects the inventory choices they make. This approach, in general, offers valuable insights on how best to manage inventories for things that deteriorate gradually. It achieves this by taking into account a number of variables related to financial flexibility and the relationships that exist between merchants and suppliers.

11. FUTURE SCOPE

The concept exhibits considerable promise for future development and implementation across several industrial domains. An aspect that might be further developed is the integration of machine learning algorithms and real-time data analytics in order to enhance the precision of demand pattern predictions and dynamically modify inventory levels. This would allow for a more responsive and effective inventory management system by adjusting to the shifting market conditions. The inclusion of environmental considerations and sustainability in the framework might be another future development. This might include methods for cutting down on waste, making the best use of available resources, and minimizing the negative effects that inventory management practices have on the environment.

Additionally, a feasibility study of the model across a range of sectors, such as pharmaceuticals, fast-moving consumer goods, and perishables, might provide insightful data on the challenges and opportunities particular to each industry. This might lead to the development of customized models that are made to meet the unique needs of these industries. In summary, improving the model's ability to take into consideration the complexities of cross-border logistics, currency fluctuations, international trade laws, and other global supply chain dynamics could make it more robust and useful in an increasingly interconnected business environment. This would be particularly relevant in a time when supply networks are becoming more interconnected and complex.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS:

Disclosure of potential conflicts of interest: Authors declare that the publishing of this paper is devoid of any conflicts of interest.

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